

Synthesis, Characterisation and Testing of some New 7,8-Dimethoxy-3-substituted-aminomethyl- 4-methylcoumarins as Possible Antibacterial Agents[†]

RAJEEV VYAS, SANGITA BAPAT and R. H. MEHTA*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

Manuscript received 25 August 1989, accepted 22 January 1990

Some new 7,8-dimethoxy-3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-methylcoumarins have been synthesised by condensation of the 7,8-dimethoxy-3-chloromethyl-4-methylcoumarin with various amines. Their structures were established by analytical and spectral data. Some of the compounds were found active against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*.

COUMARIN derivatives are known to have various biological activities¹. Recently many coumarin derivatives having amino, aminomethyl and substituted-amide group in 3-position of coumarin ring are reported to have antibacterial and antifungal activity². Moreover, presence of methoxy groups on the benzene nucleus in the coumarin ring is found to have significant physiological activity³. These observations led us to synthesise some new 7,8-dimethoxy-3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-methylcoumarin derivatives and evaluate their antibacterial activity.

7,8-Dimethoxy-4-methylcoumarin and 7,8-dimethoxy-3-chloromethyl-4-methylcoumarin were prepared according to the reported method⁴. 7,8-Dimethoxy-3-chloromethyl-4-methylcoumarin (2) on condensation with aliphatic, aromatic and heterocyclic primary and secondary amines furnished the corresponding 7,8-dimethoxy-3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-methylcoumarins (3) (Scheme 1).

The structure of the compounds have been established by elemental spectral data.

Experimental

All melting points recorded are uncorrected. Microanalysis of compounds were performed on a Coleman instrument. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through tlc.

7,8-Dimethoxy-3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-methylcoumarins (3a-v): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and the appropriate amine (0.01 mol) dissolved in dry benzene or absolute alcohol and refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The separated solid was recrystallised from proper solvent to give the title compounds (Table 1).

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of 3a-v exhibited bands at 1704-1720 (C=O of coumarin ring⁵), 1600 (aromatic C=C ring stretch) and 2900-2950 cm⁻¹ (C-H stretch of alkyl groups). Characteristic absorption band at 3350-3400 cm⁻¹ was observed for compounds prepared using primary amines.

Strong and sharp peaks observed at 650-800 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl) of chloromethyl compound (2) were not present in the aminomethyl compounds (3a, 3d-t) formed from it. Instead new peaks were

[†] Paper presented at the National Seminar on "Current Research in Heterocyclic Chemistry", Tiruchirappalli, 1989

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3a-v)*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	M p. ^{**} °C	Mol. formula
3a	H	C ₆ H ₅	187 ^a	C ₁₉ O ₄ NH ₁₉
3b	H	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	231 ^b	C ₁₉ O ₄ NH ₁₉ Br
3c	H	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	140 ^c	C ₁₉ O ₄ NH ₁₉ Cl
3d	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	180 ^d	C ₂₀ O ₄ NH ₂₁
3e	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	145 ^a	C ₂₀ O ₄ NH ₂₁
3f	H	β -Naphthyl	233 ^a	C ₂₃ O ₄ NH ₂₁
3g	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	196 ^c	C ₂₀ O ₄ NH ₂₁
3h	H	<i>p</i> -COOC ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	225 ^a	C ₂₂ O ₆ NH ₂₃
3i	H	<i>p</i> -COOCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	210 ^a	C ₂₀ O ₄ NH ₂₁
3j	H	<i>m</i> -COOCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	180 ^a	C ₂₀ O ₄ NH ₂₁
3k	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	206 ^a	C ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ H ₁₉
3l	C ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	150 ^a	C ₂₁ O ₄ NH ₂₃
3m	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	154 ^a	C ₂₀ O ₄ NH ₂₁
3n	CH ₃	CH ₃	206 ^e	C ₁₆ O ₄ NH ₁₉
3o		Piperidine	141 ^a	C ₁₀ O ₄ NH ₁₀
3p		2-Methylpiperidine	206-07 ^a	C ₁₀ O ₄ NH ₁₂
3q		3-Methylpiperidine	142 ^a	C ₁₀ O ₄ NH ₁₂
3r		4-Methylpiperidine	142 ^a	C ₁₀ O ₄ NH ₁₂
3s		Morpholine	150 ^a	C ₁₀ O ₄ NH ₁₂
3t		<i>N</i> -Phenylpiperazine	212 ^a	C ₂₃ O ₄ N ₂ H ₂₄
3u	H	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	180 ^a	C ₁₉ O ₄ NH ₁₇ Cl ₂
3v	H	3,4-Dichlorophenyl	170 ^a	C ₁₉ O ₄ NH ₁₇ Cl ₂

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis. Yields 60-80%.

**Solvent for crystallisation: ^aethanol, ^bDMF+water, ^cbenzene+petroleum ether, ^dbenzene ^epetroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°).

observed at 1175-1390 cm⁻¹ due to C-N stretching in 3. This confirmed that substituted-amino group has taken the position previously occupied by Cl.

The pmr spectrum of 2 showed the absence of a signal at δ 6.15 for C₈-H proton of 1 (Table 2), instead a new peak at δ 4.85 (C₈-CH₂-Cl) was observed. Similar peak of methylene protons

was observed at δ 4.55 for (C₈-CH₂-N<R₁) in

the spectra of 3a. The downfield shift of methylene protons in 2 to that in 3 is due to high electronegativity of chlorine atom than that of nitrogen. Thus the substitution of aminomethyl group at C₈-position in the coumarin ring is established by pmr spectral data. The other peaks in pmr spectrum of 2 were observed at δ 2.7 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 4.2 (6H, s, 2xOCH₃), 7.1 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₆-H) and 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, C₈-H).

To support the structure assigned to compound 3, additional nmr and ir spectra of important compounds are presented in Table 2.

Antibacterial activity: Some selected compounds 3b, 3c, 3k, 3m, 3o, 3t, 3u and 3v were screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method⁶ using *S. aureus* and *E. coli* as tester strains. The standard antibacterial drug used was phthalylsulphathiazole. 7,8-Dimethoxy-3-(*o*-chloro)anilino-methyl-4-methylcoumarin (3c) was found active against both *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (activity, 100 ppm concn, inhibition zone diameter 6-8 mm). 7,8-Dimethoxy-3-morpholinomethyl-4-methylcoumarin (3s), 7,8-dimethoxy-3-(*N*-phenyl)-piperizinomethyl-4-methylcoumarin (3t) and 7,8-dimethoxy-3-(*p*-nitro)-anilino-methyl-4-methylcoumarin (3k) were found

TABLE 2—IMPORTANT PMR AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME TYPICAL COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)	δ (90 MHz, CDCl ₃)	<i>m/z</i>
3a	3 400, 1 704, 1 600, 2 920, 1 300	2.75 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 4.2 (6H, s, C ₇ -C ₈ , 2xOCH ₃), 4.55 (2H, s, C ₈ -CH ₂ -N-), 6.9-7.6 (ArH, NH)	M ⁺ = 325 (70%) M ⁺ - (C ₆ H ₅ - NH) = 233 (100%) Base peak
3h	3 400, 1 705, 1 600, 2 950, 1 280	1.4 (3H, t, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.55 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 4.1 (6H, s, C ₇ -C ₈ , 2xOCH ₃), 4.25 (2H, q, -OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.45 (2H, s, C ₈ -CH ₂ -N-), 6.8-7.9 (ArH and NH)	
3l	1 704, 1 600, 2 900-2 950, 1 300	1.1 (3H, t, NOCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.45 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 3.4 (2H, q, NOCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.1 (6H, s, C ₇ -C ₈ , 2xOCH ₃), 4.45 (2H, s, C ₈ -CH ₂ -N-), 6.8-7.4 (m, ArH)	
3n	1 705, 2 920, 1 600, 1 300	2.45 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 2.55 (6H, s, N(OH) ₂), 3.52 (2H, s, C ₈ -CH ₂ -N), 4.1 (6H, s, C ₇ -C ₈ , 2xOCH ₃), 6.85 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, H-6), 7.35 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, H-5)	
1	2 900, 1 720	2.4 (3H, s, C ₄ -CH ₃), 4.0 (6H, s, 2xOCH ₃), 6.15 (1H, s, C ₈ -H), 6.85 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, C ₆ -H), 7.28 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, C ₅ -H)	

active against *E. coli* (activity, 100 ppm concn., inhibition zone diameter 6–8 mm). 7,8-Dimethoxy-3-(*p*-nitro)anilinomethyl-4-methylcoumarin (3k), 7,8-dimethoxy-3-(*p*-bromo)anilinomethyl-4-methylcoumarin (3h) and 7,8-dimethoxy-3-(3',4'-dichloro)anilinomethyl-4-methylcoumarin (3v) were found active against *S. aureus* (activity, 500 ppm concn., inhibition zone diameter 6–8 mm). Rest of the compounds were found inactive at above mentioned concentrations.

Acknowledgement

The authors are highly grateful to Prof. P. K. Bhattacharya, Head, Chemistry Department, M. S. University of Baroda, for interest in work, to Mr. Madhava Rao for microanalysis and pmr spectra and to Sushila Amin for ir spectra. The authors are also thankful to Prof. P. J. Dave of

Microbiology Department for biological screening and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (R V)

References

1. P. K. BOSE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 367, 88
KUMARI, K. S. R. K. M. RAO and N. V. SUBBA RAO, *Proc Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1961, **24**, 31.
2. G. RODIGHEIRO and G. ANTONELLO, *Bull Chem Farm* 1958, **97**, 592. M. NAGESAM, M. SUBRAMANAYAM RAJU and K. MOHANA RAJU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 418, M. AGRAWAL, S. B. BANSAL and O. P. SINGHAL, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 200. S. SHAH and R. H. MEHTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **64**, 708.
3. P. DARE, *Nature (London)* 1959, **184**, 362.
4. S. S. LELE, N. G. SAWANT and S. SETHNA, *J. Org Chem.* 1960, **25**, 1713.
5. A. R. KATRITZKY, 'Physical Methods in Heterocyclic Chemistry', Academic, New York, 1963, Vol. II, p 254.
6. P. CAVANAGH, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic, New York, 1963 p 126.